

Abstract

Tactile sensing is fundamental to human development and was among the earliest senses to evolve. Tactile perception involves a dynamical environment, continuous time, and an agent-environment coupling - neuromorphic computing excels in this domain. In this work I examine SNN Torch, nengo, reservoir computing, and the Thousand Brains Theory neuromorphic frameworks applied to a classifier from tactile data detecting changes of pressure on various textiles. I highlight the tradeoffs between these approaches in pursuit of a unified sensorimotor first neuromorphic architecture. The aim of this comparison is to build the groundwork for addressing the challenge of implementing a sensorimotor action loop.

Methods

Tactile sensor data comes at a high sampling frequency - much higher than event based vision. The touch data comes in at 20,000 Hz in a narrow voltage range of roughly $1E-3$ to $1E-2$. Given an expected range, incoming sensor values can be modified to an expected 0 to 1 range for processing via neuromorphic algorithms. In this work, data is pre-recorded and used for training offline to check for model performance. Two different data processing methods were used for the tactile data - a Fast Fourier Transform and a time interval binned aggregation of data over a specified period of time. In the time binned processing, the tactile data was reduced from 20,000 Hz to 1000 Hz or 1 data point per millisecond. The tactile dataset consists of roughly 20 samples per textile class with 20 classes.

The SNN Torch system is a simple 1 hidden layer neural network with a single LIF layer between hidden layer and output classification. The nengo system implements a Legendre Memory Unit as an early signal processing step (a polynomial approximator of input data) and feeds the signal decomposition to a population of neurons which perform a classification. The reservoir computing system is a simulation of a real world nanowire network which models the physical dynamics of the system. The Monty model implements a tactile sensor module which collects tactile data and builds an internal graph of the data via supervised offline training.

Preliminary Results

Early results show consistent and high performance for SNN Torch for all classes at 72% overall accuracy over 20 textile classes. Nengo's performance varies according to the number of classifications. Much of performance measurements are skewed by small data size. A two class classifier in nengo performs variably between 65% and 88%. A two class system reliably sits at roughly 67% (far above chance) but performance drops below 50% for higher numbers of classes. Even with separate classifier ensembles representing each class, performance remains low for higher numbers of classes.

The Legendre Memory Unit implemented in nengo however accurately models and breaks down tactile input into features. While the classification struggles at higher orders, the real-time feature extraction can be used in conjunction with SNN Torch or NengoDL to offload the classification to a standard neural network. The reservoir computing and Monty approaches are underway - reservoir computing performs on MNIST data but tactile results are still underway.

Overall this work indicates the usefulness of hybrid systems even within neuromorphic frameworks - real time processing augmented with deep learning for complicated computation is a promising avenue. Augmenting this with distributed model building akin to Monty and relying on reservoir computing units for easily trainable subpopulations within a network sketch out a burgeoning integrative neuromorphic cognitive architecture.